

UDK: 336:004.9

**ASSESSMENT OF THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESS IN THE
AZERBAIJAN FINANCIAL SYSTEM**

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Abstract. *The article assesses the current state and development directions of the digital transformation process in the Azerbaijani financial system. The level of application of digital technologies in the financial sector, especially in the banking system, the expansion of electronic financial services and the impact of innovative solutions on financial activity are analyzed. The impact of digitalization on the speed, transparency, accessibility and efficiency of financial transactions is investigated, and the risks and challenges encountered in the digital transformation process are identified. The research results show that the widespread application of modern digital technologies is of great importance for increasing the competitiveness of financial institutions, improving the quality of customer services and more effective management of financial resources. The article puts forward proposals for deeper integration of digital innovations into operational processes in order to ensure sustainable development of the financial system.*

Keywords: *digitalization process, payment infrastructure, financial relations, management, risk analysis*

Assessment of strategic priorities of digital transformation of financial relations is the process of designing, implementing and measuring the effectiveness of the impact on business activities of digital technologies that can be used at various levels of management of economic entities. Thus, such assessments can contribute to the implementation of more efficient management of economic entities, taking into account the modern conditions of digitalization [3, p.56]. It is also noted in the scientific literature that in practice, digital transformation faces many economic, technical and organizational problems [1, p. 96]. Among the problems or shortcomings that arise at the level of general management of economic entities that are participants in business relations during the implementation of business, the following can be highlighted:

- reducing the efficiency of interactions in the context of the diversity of digital tools used and requiring a single software solution;
- constantly changing levels of information security requirements;
- uncertain distribution of economic entities that form business structures and predetermine the tasks of information coordination.

In general, the process of forming a digital economy in the country is associated with significant sectoral changes in financial relations as a result of the development of modern solutions and digital production, as well as services. Thus, serious changes are taking place in the field of payments in Azerbaijan. The “payment market” is being enriched with new participants. Along with traditional participants, “Azerpocht” and various commercial banks, new payment organizations are being organized and licensed by the Central Bank. According to statistical data, it should be noted that in 2024 alone, the Central Bank issued a legal license to 14 electronic money companies, as well as one operator, to carry out the activity of providing payment services to individuals and legal entities. All this activity shows the nature and scope of changes in payments. The amount of their transactions also has an increasing trend. During the analyzed year, an amount of 61 billion Azerbaijani manats was transferred through digital money or payment companies. All this is a positive development. Of course, digitalization also brings risks and threats with it. The Central Bank is strengthening measures to combat these situations within the framework of legislation. The Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan

on “Combating the Legalization of Criminally Obtained Property and the Financing of Terrorism”, approved on December 30, 2022, creates a legal basis for implementing strict control measures over the activities of banks, investment organizations, as well as various economic entities carrying out financial transactions [5]. This legislative framework also allows for the implementation of preventive measures to timely and effectively prevent disruptive activities, as well as possible risks, against the financial system and the activities of individual economic entities.

The Central Bank, which monitors compliance with the requirements of the legislation in the field of digital payments, issued mandatory instructions to 7 economic entities in 2024. These are 3 payment companies and 4 electronic money companies, respectively. Even 1 of the electronic money companies was brought to administrative responsibility. Although at first glance the above may seem like an integral part of administrative activity, it is the application of the control mechanism through prudential regulation. In the digital transformation environment, it is important in terms of effective management of financial risks and achieving and protecting financial stability. The mentioned steps are an expression of the fact that the main financial institution of the country is implementing a policy of positive encouragement, not an oppressive position. The application of administrative responsibility shows that activities that may cause systemic damage to financial relations are strictly prevented [6, p. 85]. Such decisions create conditions for uninterrupted financing of individuals and legal entities and the smooth execution of financial transactions in the context of digital transformation. Although the mentioned decisions cause additional costs for digital financial organizations, this is an integral part of the control mechanism adopted in international practice. In general, the modern era of rapid digitalization requires supervisory authorities to be more flexible. This should also lead to the digitalization of technological and legal capabilities. The process of digitalization of financial relations should be considered not only as a process of implementation of services through digital platforms, but also as a process of improvement at the institutional level [2, p.146].

Relations in the field of financial transactions in Azerbaijan have already transitioned from prudential activity to sustainable development. Thus, integration through the application of international standards in the country, the application of advanced tools and methods in the field of combating cyber risks, as well as the general use of digital financial instruments by individuals and legal entities are observed. From the aspect of the current state of the digital transformation process in our country, the activities of the Central Bank in relation to electronic money institutions can be assessed in several ways:

1. Digital financial relations in the country are in a period of serious growth.
2. Digital development also increases parallel risks.
3. The preventive action mechanisms of financial supervisory authorities are also improving in the process of digitalization.

As we know, in addition to the human factor in the implementation of financial transactions, there are also risks arising from infrastructure. In the process of digital transformation, individuals who offer digital services and products, as well as those who consume them, have results corresponding to the state of the payment infrastructure in the country. Because the country's national payment infrastructure is a system that implements both transactions between specialized financial institutions and fast money payments. The reliability and level of development of the country's payment infrastructure affects the level and quality of digitalization in financial services. The elements of the payment infrastructure in Azerbaijan include AZIPS, LVPCSS and APS, the total amount of payments made through them in 2024 was 760 billion manat. The number of payments was 168.6 million. This indicates that the average payment is 4508 manat. Let us expand the analysis and present the turnover data carried out through the payment infrastructure in a table (Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators of transactions on the national payment infrastructure in Azerbaijan		
National Payment System participants	Number of payments (thousands)	Payment volume (million azn)

AZIPS	CB	2022	2023	2024	2022	2023	2024
	Commercial banks	14	20	20	70.984	259.382	188.603
	Other organizations	1.019	1.225	1.378	191.070	413.030	466.587
LVPCSS	CB	62	68	49	822	822	648
	Commercial banks	95.476	144.593	165.116	33.599	39.626	42.941
	Other organizations	357	375	373	7.520	8.564	9.364
APS		338	588	801	549	1.054	1.373

Source: [4, s. 6]

The indicators in table 2.2.1 allow us to better understand the directions of digitalization of financial relations. The indicators listed in the table express the dynamics of payments of both specialized financial institutions and the population, as well as state bodies. Thus, the structure of financial transactions carried out through the instant payment system allows us to analyze the financial aspects of the digital transformation in the country, mainly in terms of utility and other payments used by citizens. There has been a very serious increase here. The number of financial transactions carried out has increased by about 2.5 times. The increase in the coverage of mobile payments, as well as the increase in the number of electronic services, is the main factor increasing the use of the instant payment system. The main point is that the increase in the number of transactions is equal to the volume of payments. This is also an indicator of quality growth. In general, the improvement of the payment infrastructure leads to a reduction in risks, achievement of financial stability, and protection of the financial interests of individuals and legal entities. Summarizing the results of the analysis of indicators on other payment infrastructure elements, we can note that while the share of banks in AZIPS, a platform for large-scale financial transactions, has remained stable, the share of state institutions and large companies has increased. Inclusive development trends in the financial services sector in Azerbaijan have strengthened. Also, the increase in the number of digital services provided by banks has increased the number and volume of mainly small and medium-sized financial transactions in the AZIPS. The conducted analyses give grounds to say that the digitalization process in the financial sphere in the country has an intensive trend. Cash transactions are rapidly giving way to electronic payments. This also allows for the identification of risks in advance based on real indicators. However, at the same time, the increase in cyber risks is also inevitable. Therefore, the continuity of control and monitoring measures over financial transactions can be effectively resolved with institutional digital specialization.

Digital financial relations are deepening as a result of the intensification of the activities of both individuals and legal entities in the field of electronic payments and banking services. Since the realization of goals at the macroeconomic level is influenced by the proper organization of monetary policy, the Central Bank's ability to fully control the movement of financial resources allows it to identify and eliminate risks in a timely manner.

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